

The Excavation of the Artistic Value of Tang Dynasty Official Uniforms and the Analysis of their Influence on Modern Professional Clothing Products

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ABSTRACT

In order to explore the artistic value of official uniforms, this paper takes the clothing of the Tang Dynasty (618~907 AD) as the research object, and observes the style, material, color, heat preservation and comfort of official uniforms. Through a microscope, the materials, weaving textures, dyeing materials, styles, patterns, etc. of the Tang Dynasty official uniforms were observed, and the overall layout, mechanical balance, and gravity points of the official uniforms were tested with force detection instruments. Finally, combined with relevant literature, the value of Tang Dynasty official clothing to modern professional clothing is summarized. The results showed that the dyeing materials of the official uniforms of the Tang Dynasty were sumac, safflower, madder, bluegrass, gardenia, acacia flower, etc., and the colours were mainly purple, red and green; the materials of the official uniforms were silk, hemp silk and cotton, and the shape was triangular and trapezoidal; the center of gravity of the official uniforms was at the waist and the focus was on the shoulders. The pattern is auspicious birds and beasts such as cranes, geese, storks, peacocks, etc., and the plants are treasure flowers, twig flowers, etc.; the pattern and style of the official uniform do not affect the warmth of the official uniform and the overall warmth is reasonable. Therefore, the official uniforms of the Tang Dynasty were distinguished by color and pattern, and the pattern matching paid attention to the structural layout, which was reasonable in mechanics, style and color, and promoted the standardized development of modern professional clothing.

Keywords: Tang Dynasty Official Uniforms, Artistic Value, Modern Occupations, Apparel Products.

INTRODUCTION

As a hierarchical clothing system, the Tang Dynasty's official uniforms had obvious colour and pattern requirements, mainly three colours: red, purple and blue. Red is a member of the 3rd rank or above, purple is a member of the 5th grade, and cyan is an officer of the 5th rank or less. The official uniform of the Tang Dynasty (618~907 AD) has an essential historical connotation, which is reflected in the unification of the official uniform system in the Sui and Tang dynasties (618~907 AD) and its role in the symbolization of social class and the maintenance of political order. The official uniform of the Tang Dynasty, as the main costume of the civil and military officials to meet the emperor, can reflect the social class and political hierarchy at that time, and implement an extremely strict official hierarchy system. Officials of the 1st ~ 9th grade are required to wear official uniforms of strict distinction in colors and styles. The distinction is extremely strict and meticulous (Campa, 2023; J. Chen, Wang, Liu, Ma, & Huang, 2023), in order to better distinguish the clothing of officials, it is necessary to take the fish bag as the key, and wear the fish bag with more than 3 grades. Therefore, the fish bag was the official uniform of officials in the Tang Dynasty, and became a symbol of their social status and political power. In the Tang Dynasty, official uniforms became one of the key tools for the emperor to maintain political order and etiquette. For example, wearing a clearly defined official uniform in court meetings, diplomatic occasions, and

important ceremonial events represents a high degree of respect for the state system and imperial power (S. Chen, Dong, Chen, Xu, & Gong, 2023; Ding et al., 2023). In this way, it can be reflected that the Tang Dynasty clothing had a certain symbolic role in the national system and etiquette norms, and it played a role in maintaining and consolidating the ruling order and conveying the correct class concept at that time. The culture of the Tang Dynasty is the continuation of the culture of the Sui and Tang dynasties, and the coexistence of openness and tolerance, as well as the high degree of economic and cultural prosperity of the Tang Dynasty (618~907 AD), have made it bloom with special brilliance in Chinese history. Since the Han and Wei dynasties, the Tang Dynasty (618~907 AD) has attached great importance to its etiquette and clothing systems and is regarded as its own tradition. Based on this, the Tang Dynasty's clothing and crown system was promoted and became more complete and refined. During the Zhenguan period, cultural exchanges between the Tang Dynasty and neighbouring countries and distant countries became more and more frequent, so in the process of coming into contact with many different civilizations, they absorbed foreign cultures such as Europe and East Asia, and integrated them into the culture of Tang Dynasty society (Du et al., 2022; Hou, 2024). At the beginning of the Tang Dynasty, it was influenced by the traditional elements of the Han nationality and the Hufu style, and combined with the traditional customs of the national style. It can be seen that during the Tang Dynasty (618~907 AD), the official uniform showed a high degree of tolerance for various cultures, and had the characteristics and characteristics of inclusiveness and pluralistic symbiosis, and had strict standards. It can be seen from this that the official uniforms of the Tang Dynasty not only have a high degree of unity but also have multicultural connotations (Guo, 2022; N. Hu et al., 2023). The official uniform is a symbol of social class, a tool for maintaining political order, and a general environment that presents a pluralistic etiquette and culture, and its status is officially recognized. At the same time, it can be found from the study of the Tang Dynasty's official uniforms, which contain the cultural content of the Han nationality and other ethnic groups and have aesthetic characteristics, compatibility characteristics, and rationality. At the same time, the overall design concept of the official uniform has high artistic value and is worth digging into. This paper will dig deep into the artistic value of the Tang Dynasty official uniform (Y. Hu et al., 2023; Liu, Chen, & Tian, 2022), and focus on the analysis of its influence on modern professional clothing products, through the study of the Tang Dynasty official uniform, understand the cultural essence and characteristics of ancient Chinese clothing, and promote the inheritance of Chinese excellent traditional clothing culture. Finally, the characteristics of the Tang Dynasty's official uniforms are summarised to support the design of modern professional clothing.

METHODOLOGY

Taking the purple, red and green robes of the Tang Dynasty as examples, the materials, colors and patterns of the garments (Shenyang, Liaoning) were observed with a microscope, the heat retention and color distribution of the garments were observed with infrared equipment (Jinan, Shandong), and the mechanical distribution and center of gravity of the garments were measured by electronic scales and mechanical testers (Dongguan, Guangdong). The observation test is a non-contact test, and the sample is a replica sample, so there will be no damage to the artefacts (Y. Huang, Chen, H. Wang, & Wang, 2022; Shao et al., 2023).

RESULTS

Dyeing Materials and Shapes of Clothing

Comparing the dyeing materials of Tang Dynasty clothing, it is found that they are mainly plant dyeing, with inorganic dyes, and the results are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Clothing Dyes and Patterns

Color	Material	Grade	Pattern
Red	Suma, safflower, iron oxide, locust flower	More than 3 products	Cranes, peacocks, etc., treasure flowers
Purple	Madder, bluegrass, gardenia, copper sulfate	More than 5 products	Geese and storks are entwined with flowers
Cyan	Hematoxy, safflower, madder, bluegrass, gardenia, copper sulfate	More than 9 products	Pheasant

As can be seen from Table 1, the color of the official uniforms in the Tang Dynasty was relatively standardized, mainly because of the unified strategy of the Sui Dynasty, which strictly regulated the color and grade of the official uniforms. The use of a variety of colors characterized the official uniforms of the Tang Dynasty. The official

uniforms of the Tang Dynasty were dyed according to different fabrics, and the advantage of silk fabrics is that the texture is very soft, and the gloss is good, with excellent breathability and moisture absorption, which can be suitable to produce high-end clothing. As we all know, the social and economic conditions at that time were very good, and rich in silk, so there were many varieties of silk, high quality, including brocade, silk, silk, etc., so from the perspective of economic and technical conditions, and other conditions, the choice of silk material as the fabric of the official uniform at that time is very reasonable (Huang, Freestone, Shi, & Qian, 2023; Sheng, 2022). First, clarify the grading color system. In the design of Tang Dynasty official uniforms, the use of color needed to follow the proposed grading system strictly. For example, the color of the clothing of officials of different ranks should be seven points against each other. The color grading is reflected in its official rank. For example, the clothing of officials of the 5th and 3rd grades will be colored differently according to their official rank, and temporary officials and special officials will choose orange. In the design of Tang Dynasty official uniforms, colors and patterns were fused to form symbolic meanings, for example, purple represented nobility and respect, and auspicious birds such as cranes and storks were equipped. The emperor used yellow clothing, which symbolized the emperor's dragon power and was patterned as a dragon (Huang & Yang, 2023; Wang, Ren, & Woudstra, 2023). Then, a colorful mix. In addition to ensuring the rigor of the hierarchy and special symbolism, the official uniforms of the Tang Dynasty attached great importance to the rich and diverse overall color scheme, and maintained a certain sense of harmony, and the official uniforms were integrated with boots and waist bags (Li et al., 2023; Yuan et al., 2023). When dyeing, fusion techniques are used to balance strong color contrasts. For example, officials in the Tang Dynasty would choose official uniforms of corresponding colors according to the different seasons and occasions. In the spring, for example, officials opt for light-colored clothing to show off their vibrancy. For example, during some major festivals and celebrations, you will choose bright clothes to attend. The uniformity of the colors of the official uniforms reflects the social order and power structure of the time, and the colors of the official uniforms at all levels are clearly stipulated, reflecting the order and power structure of the Tang Dynasty society. Expressing cultural values, red, blue, and purple all have cultural meanings and values of unity, norms, and rights. For example, yellow and purple need to be dyed with iron oxide and sumac, while dyes are relatively scarce and belong to high-end colors, which are only used by royalty and nobles, so these special colors have noble and sacred meanings behind them. In the National Day ceremony and other important occasions, officials must wear their official uniforms correctly, respect etiquette norms and affirm national authority. In addition, it can be found that the aesthetic level of the official uniforms of the Tang Dynasty needs to be consistent with the aesthetic requirements and class of the society, and the official uniforms of the Tang Dynasty (618~907 AD) are not only a symbol of the identity and status of the officials, but also a carrier of the cultural traditions and aesthetic tastes of the time. Moreover, the official uniform blends color with shape (Runze, 2023; Zamcheck & Chen, 2023). There were many decorative techniques for official uniforms in the Tang Dynasty, for example, embroidery and silk craftsmanship were quite mature at that time and were effectively applied. The embroidery process is a process in which the delicate pattern of colored silk threads is embroidered on the fabric to achieve the effect of exquisite craftsmanship. Silk is a weaving process that uses gold and silver filigree and other colored silk threads to complete a robust three-dimensional display on the fabric. The application of these weaving techniques directly affects the display of the gorgeous artistic effect of the Tang Dynasty official uniforms.

Styling and Mechanical Testing of Official Uniforms

Comparing the shape and mechanical structure of the official uniform of the Tang Dynasty, the center of gravity of official uniform and the support point of the official uniform are identified, and the specific results are shown in [Figure 1](#).

Mechanical Testing

The Central Axis Gauge Crosses

Figure 1. Test of the Center of Gravity of the Official Uniform

As can be seen from the test results in Figure 1, the center of gravity of the Tang Dynasty official uniform was at the waist, and the main shoulders were relatively less stressed. The center of gravity of the Tang Dynasty official uniform was on the waist and hips. Among them, there is a deviation in the center of gravity of the two shoulders. The reason why the force of the official uniforms of the Tang Dynasty was balanced was mainly because of the high level of design technology. The design of the official uniforms of the Tang Dynasty mainly adopted a symmetrical and near-symmetrical layout, and attached great importance to the beauty of form. Moreover, the craftsmanship of the official uniform of the Tang Dynasty was very high, which was mainly reflected in its weaving level and embroidery and dyeing skills. Because of the prosperity of trade brought by the Silk Road, the clothing materials and technologies of the Tang Dynasty have been greatly developed. The texture, pattern, and color of the official uniforms of the Tang Dynasty have unique characteristics (Wan & Wu, 2023; Wu, 2023). For example, the

official uniforms of the Tang Dynasty are often made of high-quality silk materials. The patterns and colors of the official uniforms of the Tang Dynasty are extremely gorgeous and exquisite, which can highlight the cultural connotation and aesthetic characteristics of the time, and reflect the degree of social and economic prosperity at that time. The emperor's color was yellow, while high-ranking officials used purple, and materials such as silk were used, so the pattern was slightly lower on the clothes. For example, the dragon represented the emperor's power in the emperor's official uniform of the Tang Dynasty, and the size of the pattern was inversely proportional to its position in the official uniform. The larger the pattern, the closer it is to the waist. In addition, the center of gravity of the official uniform is concentrated on the waist, which is also influenced by Hu costumes. In the early Sui and Tang dynasties (581~907 AD), the war made the Tang Dynasty and the Western Regions closely integrated into the culture, and the official uniforms of the Tang Dynasty were integrated into different national aesthetic cultures, and the elements of exotic customs were widely collected, and at the same time (Zeng et al., 2022; Zhu et al., 2022), the official uniforms of the Tang Dynasty were effectively innovated and had a unique style. It can be seen that the official uniforms of the Tang Dynasty are unique in terms of design technology and color use, as well as the integration and innovation of patterns and symbols and culture. Moreover, the official uniform pays attention to the integration of the center of gravity and the shape, so that the shape is more reasonable, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. The Shape and Center of Gravity of Baoxianghua

Through the analysis of the shape and center of gravity of Baoxianghua, it is found that it has the characteristics of a symmetrical center of gravity and axial symmetry, and the overall situation is reasonable. It shows that the official uniforms of the Tang Dynasty are not only symmetrical in overall shape, but also symmetrical in pattern. Fabric selection and styling design. Tang Dynasty official uniforms were generally made of fine silk fabrics, and their tailoring was very elaborate to highlight officials' noble status and taste. The tailoring of the clothing worn by officials of different ranks indicates the high rigor of the hierarchy of Tang society. At the same time, the corresponding shape is designed according to different materials to enhance the rationality of the shape. The rationality of color accessories and overall shape. Judging from the accessories of the official uniforms of the Tang Dynasty, it can be seen that the designer attaches great importance to the embodiment of the image of officials. For example, the official uniforms of the Tang Dynasty attached great importance to the matching of accessories, and paid attention to exquisite styles for belts, shoes, socks, hats and other accessories, to highlight the overall modeling effect and the noble status of officials. Depending on the season and occasion, the official uniforms of Tang Dynasty officials will have different fabric and style requirements, so the shape will also change. For example, in summer, you may choose a lightweight, highly breathable silk fabric with a relatively simple shape. Secondly, the official uniforms of the Tang Dynasty had a lot of functions, as follows: different levels, the shape of the official uniforms of officials will be different, which is reflected in the tailoring design, so the complexity of the shape is also higher. For example, to highlight the difference in the status of officials, the imperial court will put forward different functional requirements, such as tailoring the design and structural shape of official uniforms to highlight the strictness of social hierarchy and low complexity of modelling. In various activities held by the

imperial court, in court meetings and in diplomatic ceremonies, wearing official uniforms in line with one's identity is a kind of respect and importance for the state system and the dignity of imperial power. This mode of highlighting the national system and etiquette norms through official uniforms.

Thermal Insulation and Comfort of Clothing

Compared with the official uniform of the Tang Dynasty, it is found to have better heat retention and stronger ventilation, indicating better comfort, and the specific results are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Heat Retention and Heat Dissipation of Clothing

As can be seen from the test results in Figure 3, the garment's heat retention is good, the overall heat dissipation is concentrated in the central position, and the heat dissipation around it is poor. And the ventilation is reflected in the heat dissipation of its body. Regarding the heat dissipation test, there are no centralized and key heat dissipation points, so the heat dissipation effect is better. Due to the different materials, patterns, and colors of clothing, a reasonable layout and design are required to improve the effects of heat dissipation and thermal insulation. The patterns and ornaments of the official uniforms of the Tang Dynasty include dragon pattern clothing, etc. Each pattern decoration will have its own application principles, symbolic meaning, and aesthetic expression, but the dragon pattern presents a large distance distribution to ensure the heat dissipation effect. In addition, dragon patterns, moire, and floral patterns all have strict hierarchical distinctions in Tang Dynasty official uniforms, and at the same time, their use has different aesthetic connotations, and the connotation is integrated with the structure of the official uniform, and the heat dissipation points are distributed in the armpits, back, etc. For example, the aesthetic connotation of the dragon pattern is to highlight the dignity of the emperor, highlighting a sense of top-level luxury and solemnity and the majesty of the dragon's face, but in order to improve comfort, the pattern is designed on the chest and waist. At the same time, the display of the dragon pattern is the love and admiration of traditional Chinese culture and myths and legends since ancient times, so comfort is improved through the large distribution of the pattern. The moire decoration can show the pursuit of elegance and temperament of the official uniforms of the Tang Dynasty and show a magnificent atmosphere and unfathomable aesthetic emotion, and the dragon pattern is distributed at a non-equidistant distance to improve the comfort of the clothing. The embroidery process has a wide range of applications in the production of official uniforms in the Tang Dynasty, which uses a variety of silk threads of different colors and textures to complete exquisite, delicate and gorgeous embroidery on the fabric, so as to show lifelike patterns and highlight the majesty and beauty of the official uniforms, and the sense of authority. The exquisite level of embroidery craftsmanship in the Tang Dynasty (618~907 AD) greatly improved the production level of Tang Dynasty official uniforms, which is one of the reasons why Tang Dynasty official uniforms were able to maintain a high artistic standard. Silk reeling

was an important technique used in the production of official uniforms in the Tang Dynasty. Silk thread is a weaving technique that uses gold and silver threads and other colored silk threads to complete three-dimensional patterns or patterns on fabrics. This process not only requires craftsmen to have a strong ability to control materials and patterns, but also requires their weaving skills to put forward high requirements. The use of silk craftsmanship made the production of official uniforms in the Tang Dynasty more luxurious and elegant, and at the same time could highlight the taste of the imperial court. On the other hand, this can reflect the economic level of Tang Dynasty society. In addition, the floral pattern reflects the pursuit of natural beauty and humanistic feelings in the official uniforms of the Tang Dynasty, and through delicate and delicate embroidery, the fresh and elegant aesthetic taste of the official uniforms of the Tang Dynasty is displayed, and the embroidery method is relatively unique, as shown in [Figure 4](#).

Needle and Thread Crossing

Pattern Articulation

[Figure 4](#). Weaving of Official Uniforms

As can be seen from [Figure 4](#), the pattern of the official uniform is a longitudinal cross weave, so it can improve the comfort of the clothing. The textile technology of the Tang Dynasty society was very mature and complex. At that time, the textile process mainly included warp and weft staggered weaving techniques and color pattern weaving techniques. Among them is a special "silk" weaving technique, which can form a very three-

dimensional pattern on the silk. The brocade technique can be used to form gorgeous, intricate patterns through the staggered weaving of various colored wires. Through the application of some high-level textile techniques and techniques, the official uniforms of the Tang Dynasty can show an extraordinary and luxurious temperament, and show excellent taste and quality. Third, the gorgeous display of official uniforms from the Tang Dynasty benefited from the development of many innovative textile technologies. For example, the emergence of some sophisticated shuttles and jacquard machines made the patterns of Tang Dynasty official uniforms more exquisite and complex, and in order to improve the production standards at that time, the Tang Dynasty had a special agency responsible for managing and supervising the production quality and production process of official uniforms. Based on this, the silk industry and related technology in the Tang Dynasty reached a new peak, thus providing a more complete system and technology for the production of official uniforms in the Tang Dynasty. It can be seen that the weaving technology of the official uniform in the Tang Dynasty was reasonable and could improve the ventilation and thermal insulation effect of the official uniform.

THE INFLUENCE OF TANG DYNASTY OFFICIAL UNIFORM ART ON MODERN PROFESSIONAL WEAR DESIGN

Improve the Color Recognition of Modern Professional Wear

First of all, the principle of color matching must be applied. First, the Tang Dynasty official uniforms had a strict hierarchy of color application, which profoundly impacted the design of modern professional attire, reflected in the different dress codes of various industries and positions in the design of modern professional attire. For example, industries with more rigorous and stable requirements, such as finance and law, mainly use more stable colors such as black and dark blue to demonstrate the wearer's professionalism and authority. Creative industries, for example, tend to choose brighter and more lively colors to reflect their identity. Second, the use of colors in Tang Dynasty official uniforms attached great importance to harmony and contrast. Applying this principle to the design of modern workwear is characterized by a strong grasp of color contrast and lightness. For example, modern professional wear designers will improve the visual impact of professional wear through reasonable color contrast and collocation, and on this basis, ensure the harmony of the overall dress, so that it has a unified color effect. Third, seasonal changes in official uniforms of the Tang Dynasty will be considered in the choice of colors. This principle is applied to the design of modern professional wear, which reflects that the designer will adjust the color of the dress according to the change of seasons, not only to adapt to the comfort requirements required by the changing climate, but also to adapt to the fashion needs of the wearer.

Secondly, the shaping of professional image. First, in terms of the requirements for creating a professional image, the official uniforms of the Tang Dynasty would distinguish ranks and identities through specific colors. Based on this, designers of modern professional wear will take this principle into account and standardize the dress code to enhance the sense of collaboration among team members, at the same time, designers will improve the image of the wearer through the design of professional clothing, so that customers can trust the business ability of enterprises and individuals more. Second, in terms of showing personal taste, Tang officials would show their unique aesthetic and status through elaborate and culturally rich clothing, which was mainly reflected in the clothing of some relatively loose occasions. At present, professional wear designers will help show their unique personality and taste through the design of reasonable business formal wear and business casual wear. Third, adapt to various occasions. At this point, Tang officials would choose clothing in the style and color that matched them according to different occasions. Based on this, modern professionals can choose their attire in business activities according to different occasions. For example, professionals can choose more serious clothing for meetings and negotiations. For example, in daily office work or internal activities of enterprises, professionals should choose relatively casual clothing. It can be seen that the color use and image shaping of the official uniforms of the Tang Dynasty are extremely particular, and this application principle has been used for a certain reference in the design of modern professional clothing. Through the study, understanding and application of the color matching principle and image shaping art of the Tang Dynasty, modern professional wear designers can better exert their talents and show more diverse and personalized professional wear design works; the structure and shape of the Tang Dynasty official uniform are extremely exquisite and exquisite, which can provide a model for the professional wear design of later generations and influence the professional wear design concept of later generations. At the same time, the protection and inheritance of official uniforms in the Tang Dynasty can play a role in the protection and inheritance of ancient Chinese clothing culture, and form a positive and shining model.

Pay Attention to the Role of Tang Dynasty Pattern Decoration in Modern Professional Clothing

There are many patterns and decorative elements in Tang Dynasty clothing, and the elements can be applied

to the design of modern professional clothing. The motifs of the official uniforms of the Tang Dynasty can be interpreted in a simplified way in modern professional attire design. For example, the moire and floral patterns common on the official uniforms of the Tang Dynasty can be simplified into more abstract shapes or lines, and patterns, logos and other methods can be displayed on professional clothing. In this way, it can retain the connotation of traditional Chinese culture and represent the simple aesthetics of modern people. At the same time, this can improve the fashion and generous charm of modern professional wear design, and convey the protection, inheritance and respect of the excellent traditional Chinese culture in the corporate culture; For example, designers can use the current digital printing technology to draw some of the pattern elements in the official uniforms of the Tang Dynasty on the professional wear, so that the clothes have a certain historical and cultural heritage and highlight the characteristics of modernization. For example, on the neckline or cuffs of the suit, the embroidery process of the Tang Dynasty official uniform pattern can highlight the rigorous image of professional clothing and maintain a sense of refinement; With effective cross-border integration, designers can combine other cultural elements to highlight the sophisticated style of modern professional wear. For example, designers can add the wide cuffs or neckline design of Tang Dynasty official uniforms to the design of Western-style professional clothing, or combine the floral patterns of Tang Dynasty official uniforms with the current popular geometric shapes to make fabric prints. Based on this, in the process of retaining the essence of traditional aesthetics, such as some modern aesthetic thinking concepts, the design of modern professionals should have a more elegant temperament and aura and highlight the profession. In this way, the design quality of modern professional wear can be improved, and the enterprise's cultural connotation and brand value can be improved. The official uniform is very particular about details and craftsmanship, which can show the full respect for traditional culture at that time, and at the same time, show the expectation of continuous inheritance of traditional culture. In the design of modern professional wear, designers can get inspiration from the relevant elements of Tang Dynasty official uniforms and get some inspiration. For example, designers can incorporate some traditional cultural elements of the Tang Dynasty's official uniforms into their designs to show respect, protection, and inheritance of excellent traditional Chinese culture. Second, the pursuit of dignity and elegance. The official uniforms of the Tang Dynasty were of great importance to the dignified and elegant design style; for example, their reasonable tailoring and exquisite craftsmanship could show unique taste. This design concept can influence modern workwear design. For example, designers can highlight the elegance and dignity of the position through the use of the design concept, for which the designer can try to improve the dignity and elegance of his design works to show the professional's generosity and decency.

Inject Modern Colors and Design Elements

Modern professional wear designers can effectively blend traditional colors with modern color theories to create a modern and traditional color system. For example, modern professional wear designers can reinterpret the colors of emerald green and sapphire blue in Tang Dynasty official uniforms through modern color matching techniques. Second, pattern remodeling. In this regard, designers can abstract the traditional patterns of official uniforms of the Tang Dynasty so as to make them more modern and simple. In addition, designers can use digital technology to restore the classical patterns in the official uniforms of the Tang Dynasty, and then add their own aesthetic opinions to add relevant charm elements, and display them on professional clothing to present a delicate new classic pattern. Third, is material fusion. Modern workwear designers can combine traditional fabrics such as silk or satin with smart fabrics and new recycled fabrics to create a unique modern texture, which retains the traditional texture and increases functionality. This design concept has clearly influenced the design of modern business wear. Modern professional attire generally attaches great importance to the slenderness, straightness and neatness of the shoulder line, based on which it can show the professional and stable image of the professional. The Tang Dynasty official uniform attaches great importance to the line design of the waist, and generally speaking, the Tang Dynasty official uniform designers will show the official's posture curve through reasonable tailoring and beautiful waist design. This approach can have an enlightening effect on the design of modern workwear. In the current professional wear design, many designers will prioritize the design of the waist line, and pay attention to highlighting the curve of the waist through reasonable tailoring, to show professionalism elegance and dignity. Third, the sleeve design. The sleeve design concept of the Tang Dynasty official uniform is very unique. Generally speaking, Tang Dynasty official uniforms attach great importance to the smoothness of the lines of the sleeve design, and pay attention to the neat and neat design style, so the Tang Dynasty official uniforms like to use wide sleeve design or folding sleeve design. Based on this, modern professional wear designers will take this design concept into account and apply it to the design of modern professional wear. For example, some modern professional wear designers incorporate wide-sleeved designs into their creations to show the smoothness and cleanliness of the sleeve lines and highlight the elegant professional image, while Tang Dynasty official uniforms have a high pursuit of fabrics, cuts and patterns, especially great attention to detail and quality. Based on this, designers of modern professional wear can refer to this kind of thinking, and in the

selection of fabrics and tailoring technology, try to pursue details to achieve excellence and improve the quality of modern professional wear. Fourth, embody identity and status. Tang Dynasty official uniforms often used different colors and patterns to show the status of officials. Based on this, designers of modern professional wear can refer to this kind of thinking, and reflect the professional identity and department level of the professional through different colors and patterns.

CONCLUSION

The official uniform of the Tang Dynasty has high artistic value, which is mainly reflected in the shape, color, mechanical balance, and heat preservation, and can influence the design of modern professional clothing products, so as to play a certain role in the further innovation of modern professional clothing design. Through research, it was found that the design of the official uniforms of the Tang Dynasty had a very strict hierarchical distinction, using red, blue and cyan as the basis, and with patterns such as cranes and peacocks, and integrating Baoxiang flowers and tangled branches into the patterns. In the pattern design, the pattern, color and shape are integrated, the force points are distributed on the shoulders, and the center of gravity is on the waist. At the same time, the distribution between the patterns and the integration of shapes contrast with the styles to improve the comfort and heat preservation of the official uniform. Therefore, the design of modern professional wear can be combined with the color and pattern concept in the design of official uniforms in the Tang Dynasty to carry out more innovation, so as to achieve the purpose of protecting and inheriting traditional Chinese culture, and effectively improve the taste and texture of modern professional wear design. This study has some shortcomings, mainly because it is difficult to collect data on official uniforms, and the measurement and collection of official uniforms are limited. In future research, we should focus on the value mining of official uniforms and improve the relevant content.

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